

DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MICONAZOLE NITRATE NANOPARTICLES LOADED GEL

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the development and characterization of Miconazole Nitrate-loaded chitosan nanoparticles prepared by the ionic gelation method and their incorporation into a Carbopol 934-based gel for topical antifungal therapy. Miconazole Nitrate, a broad-spectrum antifungal drug, was encapsulated within chitosan nanoparticles to enhance its solubility, stability, and skin permeability. The optimized formulation (F1) showed favourable physicochemical characteristics, including uniform particle size, high entrapment efficiency, and good stability. The nanoparticle-loaded gels F1G1–F1G4 were evaluated for pH, viscosity, spreadability, and extrudability, which were within acceptable limits for topical application. *In-vitro* drug release studies demonstrated a biphasic pattern with an initial burst followed by sustained release up to 12 hours, governed by a Higuchi diffusion-controlled mechanism. Among all

formulations, F1G1 exhibited the highest cumulative release of 92.35%. The *In-vitro* antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* revealed that the nanoparticle-loaded gels produced a larger zone of inhibition compared to the pure drug and control, indicating superior efficacy. Overall, the developed Miconazole Nitrate nanoparticle-loaded gel exhibited controlled and sustained release, improved antifungal activity, and enhanced patient compliance, suggesting its potential as an effective topical drug delivery system for fungal infections.

KEYWORDS: Miconazole Nitrate, Chitosan Nanoparticles, Ionic Gelation, Topical Drug Delivery, Antifungal Activity, *Candida albicans*.

INTRODUCTION

Topical drug delivery can be defined as the application of a medication to the skin or mucous membrane for local or systemic action. Delivery of drugs via skin is effective and avoids first-pass effect and metabolic degradation associated with oral administration.^[1] Development of successful topical drug delivery system has been limited in scope due to the significant penetration barrier provided by the stratum corneum, the topmost skin layer. To overcome this barrier, numerous active and passive penetration enhancement methods have been assessed. Although active methods including iontophoresis, electroporation, and micro needles have shown some efficiency, more work is needed to establish for their safety band and cost effectiveness. Passive methods include the use of chemical penetration enhancers, supersaturated systems, prodrugs, liposomes, micro emulsions, and colloidal polymeric suspensions. This approach provides design flexibility (with formulation optimization) and the possibility of application over a larger area of skin compared to active methods. Chemical penetration enhancers have been intensively investigated over the years, but the concentrations required for improved penetration often lead to irritation or sensitization. The use of vesicular delivery systems such as liposomes, transfersomes, ethosomes, and niosomes is still limited due to stability issues and insufficient understanding of the mechanism of penetration across intact skin. Additionally, lipid based colloidal carriers (solid lipid nanoparticles, nanostructured lipid carriers, and lipid nanocapsules) have shown improved drug penetration through skin, but their limited drug loading and the phase stability remain to be addressed, restricting their clinical applicability. Researchers have carried work in formulating the nanoparticulate system of gallic acid (GA) in the form of glutathione responsive disulfide cross-linked poly(ethylene glycol)-based gels.^[2] Nanoparticles based on biocompatible and biodegradable synthetic or semi-synthetic polymers have shown promise in dermal drug delivery. These types of carriers can potentially enhance the permeation of drug into deeper layers of skin and reduce skin irritation. Dispersion of polymer-based nanoparticles in hydrophilic gels can further improve drug delivery to the skin. The gel can aid in creating a uniform dispersion of the carriers in the matrix and increase the contact time and deposition of the carriers on the skin, resulting in enhanced skin penetration of the payload.^[3]

Miconazole nitrate is -1-[2-(2,4-dichloro-phenylmethoxy)-2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)ethyl]-1H-imidazole nitrate. A white or almost white, crystalline or microcrystalline powder and belongs to BCS CLASS II. Miconazole nitrate is one of the broad-spectrum antifungal compounds of

the imidazole group. This antifungal agent is a fungicide used in the treatment of fungal infections in a topical and transdermal.^[10] This drug works by inhibiting ergosterol biosynthesis on the fungal cell membranes that cause damage to the cell wall of the fungus, resulting in increased membrane permeability, and ultimately, causing the fungal cell to lose its cellular nutrients. The drug is mainly used for the treatment of mycosis skin diseases.^[4]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Miconazole Nitrate was received as a gift sample from Mahrshee Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. Bharuch, Gujarat, India. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, sodium hydroxide and were purchased from thermo fisher scientific India Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore, India. The distilled water was produced in our research laboratory with a distillation unit.

Method of Preparation

Ionic Gelation Technique

Chitosan nanoparticles were formulated by ionic cross linking of chitosan solution with TPP anions. Chitosan was dissolved in aqueous solution of acetic acid (0.2,v/v) at different concentrations such as 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 mg/ml. Under magnetic stirring at room temperature, 5 ml of 0.84% (w/v) TPP aqueous solution was added dropwise using syringe needle into 10 ml chitosan solution containing 10mg of Miconazole Nitrate. pH was adjusted to 6.0 by adding 0.1 M NaOH. The stirring was carried about 30 min. The prepared nanoparticles suspensions were centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 30 min using C24 centrifuge. The formation of the particles was a result of the interaction between the negative groups of the TPP and the positively charged amino groups of chitosan (Ionic gelation).^[5]

Preparation of Miconazole Nitrate Nanoparticle Loaded Gel^[6,7]

Gel was prepared by dissolving carbopol polymer in distilled water and stirred until it formed a clear transparent gel. pH was adjusted to 5.5 with triethanolamine and allowed to stand for 24 h at room temperature. Then finally drug loaded nanoparticles were incorporated in gel.

Table 1: Formulation of Miconazole Nitrate nanoparticle loaded gel.

Sl. No.	Formulation Code	Carbopol 934 (% w/v)	Triethanolamine (ml)	Water
1	F1G1	1.0	0.3	q.s
2	F1G2	1.5	0.3	q.s
3	F1G3	2.0	0.3	q.s
4	F1G4	2.5	0.3	q.s

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

Identification of drug

Melting point determination

Capillary method was used for the determination melting point of Miconazole Nitrate. A few crystals of compound are placed in a thin-walled capillary tube of about 10-15 cm long and 1 mm inside diameter and closed at one end. The capillary tube which contains the sample and a thermometer are then suspended in to an oil bath containing liquid paraffin. So, they can be heated slowly and evenly. The temperature range over which the sample is observed to melt is taken as the melting point.

Solubility analysis^[8]

Solubility analysis was carried out for Miconazole Nitrate sample by preparing saturated solution in water, methanol and various buffers pH 4.4, pH 5.4, pH 6.8, and pH 7.4 and kept it for overnight and then the absorbance was taken by using UV- Spectrophotometer.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)^[9]

DSC thermograms of pure drugs were performed by using an automatic thermal analyzer system (Mettler DSC 823, Germany). The entire samples run at a scanning rate of 10 °C per min from 25-300 °C.

Drug-excipients interactions studies by FTIR^[10]

Drug-excipient compatibility studies were carried out by FTIR (Shimadzu I R, Japan). Infrared spectrum of pure drug (Miconazole nitrate) and physical mixture of drug and polymer were carried out to investigate any changes in chemical composition. Using potassium bromide (KBr) pellet method and recorded pellets were scanned using FT-IR spectrophotometer in the range of 400- 4000cm⁻¹.

Standard calibration curve of Miconazole Nitrate

100 mg of accurately weighed Miconazole Nitrate was dissolved in 10ml of methanol and make up to 100 ml by pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solutions. 10 ml of the above solution was diluted to 100 ml of pH 6.8. From the above solution 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 µg/ml was prepared and analyzed by UV spectrophotometer at λ -max 272nm. The graph of absorbance v/s concentration in µg/ml was plotted and r² value of this graph was calculated to check the linearity of the absorbance against concentration.

Evaluation Of Miconazole Nitrate Nanoparticles Loaded Gel^[11-14]

Physical examination

The physical appearance of color, consistency texture and greasiness these all features were done for topical gel formulation.

Determination of pH

1 ml of the prepared gels was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask, and the solution was diluted with distilled water. The pH of the resulting solution was determined using a digital pH meter.

Viscosity

The viscosity of the nanogel systems was determined using a Brookfield viscometer coupled with an S-94 spindle (Brookfield Engineering Laboratories Inc., MA, USA). The prepared gel formulations were transferred to the beaker. The spindle was lowered perpendicularly into the gel at 100 rpm and temperature was maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C. The viscosity was determined during the cooling of the system.

Spreadability

Spreadability was performed by using two glass slides of length 7.5 cm. 350 mg of topical gel was weighed accurately and its was taken on one glass slide. Another glass slide was placed above it from a height of 5 cm. A weight of 5 gm was kept on the upper slide and after 1 min, diameter of circle that was spread was noted in cm. The observed diameter indicates the type of gel.

Extrudability

Extrudability test was carried out by using Pfizer hardness tester. gel was filled in collapsible aluminium tube. The plunger was adjusted to hold the tube properly the pressure of 1kg/cm² was applied for 30 sec. The quantity of the gel extruded was weighed. The procedure was repeated at three equidistance places of the tube. The test was carried out in triplates.

In vitro diffusion study

In vitro diffusion study of formulated gels was carried out on the franz diffusion cell. Franz diffusion membrane was used as a diffusion membrane. The diffusion cell was filled with phosphate buffer pH 6.8, diffusion membrane was mounted on the cell. The temperature was maintained at 34-37°C. At predetermined time points, 5 ml samples were withdrawn from the

acceptor compartment, replacing the sampled volume with phosphate buffer pH 6.8, after each sampling, for a period of 12 hrs. The samples withdrawn were filtered and used for analysis. Blank samples were run simultaneously throughout the experiment to check for any interference. The amount of diffused drug was determined at 272 nm using on UV visible spectrophotometer, Shimadzu UV 1800.

Kinetic modelling

In order to understand the kinetic and mechanism of drug release, the result of in vitro drug release study of nanoparticles was fitted with various kinetic equation like zero order (cumulative% release vs. time), first order (log% drug remaining vs. time), Higuchi's model (cumulative% drug release vs. square root of time), Peppas plot (log of cumulative% drug release vs. log time). R2 (coefficient of correlation) and k (release rate constant) values were calculated for the linear curve obtained by regression analysis of the above plots.^[15]

In-vitro antifungal studies

Sterile Nutrient Agar plates were prepared, by pouring the sterile agar into petri dishes under aseptic conditions. 0.1ml of the test organism (*Candida albicans*) spread on agar plates. 5 mm diameter holes were made in the agar plates using a sterile bore. 500 µg/ml of drug, F1G1-F1G4, F1 and DMSO were added into each hole separately. All the plates containing *Candida albicans* were incubated at 37°C for 24 hrs. Zone of inhibition of microbial growth around the well were measured and recorded after the incubation time.^[16]

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

Identification of drug

Melting point determination

The melting point of the Miconazole Nitrate was determined by the Thieles tube method and DSC the results are shown in Fig.

Table 2: Melting point report of Miconazole Nitrate.

Reported	Method	Observed		
		Trail 1	Trail 2	Trail 3
178-184 ⁰ C	Thieles Tube method	178°C	180°C	178°C
	DSC	180.27°C		

Fig. 1: DSC Graph of Pure Drug.

Standard calibration curve of Miconazole Nitrate

Miconazole Nitrate obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 0-25 μ g/ml at λ max 272 nm in pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer with regression of coefficient (r^2) of 0.9996 and slope (m) of 0.0337 UV spectra of different concentrations. plot of calibration curve was constructed in Fig 2.

Fig. 2: Plot of standard calibration curve of Miconazole Nitrate.

Compatibility studies by FTIR spectrophotometer

FTIR analysis of the pure drug and its physical mixture showed characteristic peaks of functional groups (N-H, C-H, C=C, N=O, C-O, C-N, and C-Cl) with only minor shifts in

wave numbers. Specifically, the C–H bending appeared at 764.42 cm^{-1} (pure drug) and 763.12 cm^{-1} (mixture), while the C–Cl stretching was observed at 632.23 cm^{-1} and 635.10 cm^{-1} , respectively. These minimal changes indicate no chemical interaction or structural alteration, confirming the stability and compatibility of the drug with the excipients.

Fig. 3: FTIR Spectra Of Pure Miconazole Nitrate.

Fig. 4: FTIR spectra of Miconazole Nitrate and physical mixture.

Evaluation of Miconazole Nitrate gel

The optimized formulation F1 was incorporated into the gel by the use of Carbopol 934

polymer and was found to be suitable for topical delivery because of the desirable consistency.

Table 3: pH, Viscosity, Spreadability of gel.

Code	pH	Viscosity(cps)	Spreadability gm*cm/sec	Extrudability
F1G1	6.31	10550±55.10	7.87±0.1	***
F1G2	6.41	10650±80.0	7.05±0.2	**
F1G3	6.45	10750±60.5	5.29±0.3	**
F1G4	6.51	11400±85.5	3.41±0.2	**

NOTE: Satisfactory*, Good**, Excellent***.

In-vitro drug release profile

The *In vitro* drug release study of Miconazole Nitrate nanoparticle-loaded gels (F1G1–F1G4) exhibited a biphasic pattern with an initial burst followed by sustained release over 12 hours. The cumulative drug release ranged from 92.35% F1G1 to 83.45% F1G4. The burst phase resulted from surface-associated drug, while the sustained phase was governed by diffusion through the Carbopol matrix. The results indicate that Increasing polymer concentration elevated viscosity and slowed diffusion, producing a more controlled release. Among all formulations, F1G1 displayed the fastest release, whereas F1G3 and F1G4 showed sustained profiles. These findings indicate that polymer concentration effectively influences release kinetics, supporting the potential of this system for prolonged topical antifungal therapy.

Fig. 5: Comparative *In vitro* drug release profiles of Miconazole Nitrate gel.

F1G1 - F1G4 formulations**Release kinetics profile of Miconazole Nitrate nanoparticles loaded gel**

The *in vitro* drug release of formulations F1G1–F1G4 predominantly followed Higuchi kinetics ($r^2 = 0.985–0.997$), indicating diffusion-controlled mechanisms. Zero-order kinetics ($r^2 = 0.967–0.988$) suggested relatively constant release, while first-order kinetics ($r^2 = 0.945–0.959$) indicated minimal concentration dependence. Korsmeyer-Peppas analysis showed n values of 0.600–0.654, signifying anomalous (non-Fickian) transport, where both diffusion and polymer relaxation contribute to release. Among the formulations, all batches demonstrated controlled and sustained drug release profiles, with slight variations in release rate and mechanism.

Fig. 6: Zero order release kinetic profile of gel F1G1-F1G4 formulations.

Fig. 7: First order release kinetic profile of gel F1G1-F1G4 formulations.

Fig. 8: Higuchi release kinetic profile of gel F1G1-F1G4 formulations.

Fig. 9: Peppas's release kinetic profile of gel F1G1-F1G4 formulations.

***In-vitro* Antifungal Effect Studies**

In-vitro antifungal effect of nanoparticles gel formulations, nanoparticle, active pharmaceutical ingredient, and DMSO was determined by using agar well diffusion method against fungal strain *Candida albicans*. At concentrations 500 µg/ml of drug, F1G1-F1G4, F1. results are shown below in table 4.

Table 4: Report of antifungal activity against *C. albicans*.

Sl. No	Samples	Zone of inhibition(mm)
1.	F1G1	21
2.	F1G2	19
3.	F1G3	18

4.	FIG4	18
5.	F1	10
6.	F1	9.1
7.	API	8.2
8.	API	8.0
9.	DMSO	0

Fig. 10 (A) Fig. 11(B)

**Fig: The antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* using agar well diffusion method
A) API, F1, F1G1, F1G2, Control. B) API, F1, F1G3, F1G4, Control.**

CONCLUSION

The study successfully developed Miconazole Nitrate-loaded chitosan nanoparticles using the ionic gelation method and incorporated them into a Carbopol gel for topical delivery. The optimized formulation showed good physical stability, controlled and sustained drug release, and enhanced antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*. The release followed the Higuchi diffusion model, indicating a diffusion-controlled mechanism. Overall, the nanoparticle loaded gel proved to be a promising topical antifungal system with improved efficacy and patient compliance compared to conventional formulations.

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